

HISTORICAL GEOGRAPHY OF RURAL AREAS OF THE NORTHERN KARATAG RIDGE OF NURATA

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the geographical location of the Republic and its convenience, deserts and mountains through this location. He also spoke about the diverse nature, atmosphere, mountain features of the Nurata Range, as well as the uniqueness of the Karatag Range.

The Nurata Mountains are the north-western branch of the Turkestan ridge. In Navoi, Samarkand and Jizzakh regions. In the southeast, the Ilonotti mountain range on the Sangzor River separates the Nurata Mountains from the Molguzar Range. It is bordered on the south by the Zarafshan basin and on the north by the Kyzylkum desert. The Nurata Mountains consist of two parallel ridges.

The northern ridge is called the Nurata Mountains, more precisely the Nurata Mountains, and the south is called the Southern Nurata Mountains. The north-eastern part of the Nurata Mountains is occupied by the Koytash Mountains. The Koytash Mountains run from the Sovurbel Pass in the northwest to the Sangzor River in the southeast. Uz. 70 km, average height 1260 m. The central part of the North Nurata Range is relatively high, averaging 1,750 m. The highest point (Zar-gartog) is 2169 m. In this part there are such peaks as Big Fo-zilmon

(2134 m), Qarchigay (2105 m). The north-western part of the Nurata Mountains is not very high, with an average altitude of 900–1100 m. The Southern Nurata Mountains are bordered by several meridian valleys; It consists of Gubdintog, Qaraqchitog, and Aktag, which extend from south-east to north-west. Karatag, northwest of Aktag, is also part of the southern Nurata Mountains. These mountains are separated by Koshrabat, Koytash and Nurata. The Nurata Mountains stretch 180 km to the northwest. The average height is 1000–1500 m. It consists of Paleozoic limestone, sandstone and shale, metamorphic rocks. There are a lot of horses among them. Neogene and Quaternary deposits are also common in the lower parts of the southern ridges and in the Bots. Tectonically, the ridges have a meganticline structure, formed by Hercynian deformation and rising to their current height as a result of new tectonic movements.

Figure 1. Location of Nurata region

In the lower reaches of the Nurata Mountains, summers are dry and hot, and winters are not so cold. The climate is cool on the slopes and in the upper parts, with more precipitation. The average annual temperature is 13.4-14.4 °, -0.6 ° -2.3 ° in January, and 15 ° -25.4 ° in July. The highest temperature is 46 ° -47 ° in the foothills, the lowest is -29 °, -30 °. Annual precipitation is 251-452 mm, snow cover is 15-30 cm. The average wind speed is 2.0-3.2 m per second, sometimes up to 28 m.

Many rivers and streams (Osmonsay, Kulbasay, Uchmasay, Majrumsay, Ukhumsay, Sentabsay, Tusunsay, Oqtepasay, Koksaroyasay, Oqchopsoy, etc.) start from the Nurata Mountains. Due to their low water consumption, when they reach the plains, they dry up or are used for irrigation. In spring, they also experience floods.

In the Nurata Mountains, mainly gray soils and brown-gray soils are found at altitudes of 1600–1700 m. Ephemeral and ephemeroids grow in the foothills and up to 1600 m. Shrubs and trees include almonds, walnuts, namatak, uchkat, hawthorn, and others. In the upper part there are spruce groves. Among the animals live wolves, foxes, hawks, rabbits, mountain goats, badgers, snakes, sparrows, hawks and others. Established in 1975, the Nurata Mountain-Walnut State Nature Reserve protects the

mountain landscape and its flora (walnut, apple, cherry, mulberry), and animals (mouflon, wild boar, fox, jay, sparrow, eagle, snake). The Nurata Mountains are used as pastures. Horticulture is practiced in the river valleys. Wheat, barley and other crops are grown on the slopes.

Uzbekistan is not only a land of ancient cities, glorious madrassas, mosques and minarets. Uzbekistan is a different climatic zone: arid deserts of Kyzylkum and Karakum, snowy Tien Shan mountain range, rivers and lakes, dark mountain forests, steppes covered with flowers in spring, environmentally harmful, but the majestic Aral Desert (in place of the dried Aral Sea) and other lands. One such landmark is the Nurata Mountains, located between the Kyzylkum Desert in the west and the Hunger Desert in the east.

This mountain range includes three ridges - Karatau, Aktau and Nuratau. However, the ridge is indistinguishable in height, and the highest point is Mount Hayotbakhshi, at an altitude of 2169 meters. However, despite the lack of interest from climbers, the Nurata Mountains attract many tourists due to their rich history, unique monuments, mild climate and healing springs.

One of the most famous monuments is "Temurid Gates". It is a small gorge on the Sanzor River that flows through the eastern part of the Nurata Mountains near Jizzakh. The gorge, 120-130 meters wide, is covered on one side with two large rocks and forms a 40-meter-long passage named after our great commander Amir Temur. On the right rock of the gates are Persian inscriptions written by the rulers who passed by: Ulugbek Guguran and Abdullakhan.

On the western slope of the Nurata Mountains is the Sarmishsay Gorge, another interesting monument. It is famous for its many petroglyphs and was found along the river of the same name. In addition, the area is

an unnatural zone, although scientists attribute this to the presence of unique chemical elements, unique climate and complex landscape. This mysterious and

little-studied country attracts not only scientists and ufologists, but also many tourists.

The Nurata Mountains are a collection of monuments, history and impressions that will be engraved in your memory for a lifetime!

Nurata consists of two low ridges. To the north of this is the Nurata Range, which rises to 2,169 meters ("Peak of Life"). The southern ridge of Mount Nurata consists of several heights: Gubduntog, Karakchitog, Oktog and Karatag. They range in height from 1,150 to 2,500 meters, and are separated by river valleys that begin on the southern slopes of the northern Nurata Mountains. The western branches of the Zarafshan ridge in the south of the Turkestan ridge are located in Uzbekistan. These are known as Chaqilqalan and Qoratepa and extend from east to west. The highest peak of Mount Chakilqalon is 2388 meters. Mount Qoratepa is separated from Mount Chakilqalon by the Takhtakaracha Pass. The height of the pass is 1679 m. The highest peak of Mount Qoratepa, west of the Takhtakaracha Pass, is Qamquton, at an altitude of 2,188 m. To the north-west of the Qoratepa Mountains is the Ziyovuddin-Zirabulak Mountains, a continuation of the Zarafshan Range. These mountains are not very high, that is, they do not exceed 1112 meters. In southern Uzbekistan, the southwestern part of the Gissar mountain

range and several of its branches are located. Upon entering the territory of Uzbekistan, the mountain changes its direction to the south-west and is divided into several mountain ranges. In the Gissar Mountains is the highest peak of Uzbekistan - "Hazrati Sultan", which is 4688 m above sea level. Each branch of Gissar Mountain has its own name. The headwaters of Kashkadarya are called Sumsar and Shertog. Their highest peak is 2,692 meters, and the western side descends. To the north-west of the Gava Pass, Hazrat Sultan Mountain, a part of the Gissar Mountains, stretches to a height of more than 4,000 meters. Several branches of the Gissar Mountains extend to the south-west. In general, they look like Mount Gissar. That's why we mention only the largest of them. These are: Bosmontash (the highest peak is 3953 m), Beshnov (3448 m), Eshan Square (2919 m), Khantakhta (2936 m), Bobo Burkhan (2476 m), Boysuntog (4424 m) and others. The south-western part of the Gissar Mountains is called Kokhitang Mountain, and its height is 3137 meters (Maychali). To the east is the Babatag Range, with a peak called Zarkosa at 2,286 meters. In the mountainous part of Uzbekistan, intermountain depressions have a special place. The formation of depressions is associated with the rise of

mountain ranges. as the ridges rose, the depressions between them began to sink, resulting in the erosion of ancient hard rock in the mountains and the accumulation of sediments in the depressions. In addition, most of the basins are surrounded by various cracks in the ground, through which the ridges rise vertically, and the basins sink. In addition, young mountains were formed in the basins themselves, which led to the formation of small anticlines and synclines. As a result, low hills and depressions appeared in the basins. The surface of all intermountain depressions is almost flat, and they slop as they approach mountain ranges. One of the largest mountain ranges in Uzbekistan is Tashkent-Mirzachol. It is bounded on the north-east and east by the Western Tianshan Mountains, on the south and south-west by the Turkestan, Molruzor and Nurata Mountains, and on the north-west by the Kyzylkum Desert..

Taking into account the diversity of lithological structure and relief, Nurata district is divided into 5 geomorphological zones:

1. White Mountains;
2. Karatag and Aktag low mountains;
3. The foothills of the Karatag Mountains;
4. Aktag, Pashat low mountains and foothill plains;
5. A wide undulating plain at the foot of a mountain.

The first geomorphological zone is the Aktag Mountains, with the Oltinsoy farm at the far end of its southeastern part, the highest peak of Aktag with a 1580-meter ridge. The Aktag Mountains stretch from southeast to northeast. The surface elevations of this area decrease to 935 m. The Bakhiltag Mountains are characterized by bare rocks and no topsoil. The slopes are steep, with peaks in some places ranging from 150 m to 450 m. Since the base of the Aktag and Bakhiltag ridges is composed of rocky rocks, vegetation is very rare here, it is found only in the lower part of the slopes and cliffs, and here it is mainly composed of wormwood, sagebrush and other ephemeral plants. The slopes range from 30% to 50% of the vegetation cover. Accordingly, it is the starting point for the development of soil cover in mountainous conditions. The soils are rocky, rough-skeletal, and under the influence of flood waters, the gravels are washed into the lowlands. In the upper layers of these deposits, the process of mechanical, chemical radiation dominates. Some of the slopes are covered with rock. The rocks are covered with sandstone and shale. The middle part of the White Mountain is made of limestone and marble. The fine soils that cover the main rocks are formed on the surface of the slopes, and at the bottom of the slope its thickness is 0.5-0.7 m.

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